

PROTECTING TREES FROM WILDLIFE AND LIVESTOCK FROM HEDGE ESTABLISHMENT

Agroforestry Guide to Preventing Damage
Caused by Wildlife in Early Years

1. Wildlife damage to trees (1- Black locust tree rubbed by a roe deer during the rutting season ; 2- Bite marks on the trunk of a Douglas fir, characteristic of winter bark stripping ; 3- The progressive and complete girdling of a plant's bark by a rabbit quickly leads to the death of the tree.) © Philippe Van Lerberghe 2. Young Plant Protection System ©Ver de Terre Production 3. T-Posts for Tree Protections ©Ver de Terre Production 4. Protection of a Hedgerow in a Managed Grazing System ©Ver de Terre Production

THE WHAT AND WHY

Protecting young trees from the moment of planting is essential to ensure their survival and optimal growth. Animals, whether wildlife, livestock, or rodents, pose a significant threat to plantations. Through their presence, feeding, and/or behavior, fauna can cause damage that reduces the current or future quantitative or qualitative yield of a woody or agricultural production. They can inflict various types of harm, such as browsing, rubbing, bark stripping, gnawing, or even the death of the plants. These damages not only impact tree growth in height and diameter but can also lead to deformations, forking, and developmental delays. Indeed, a stressed tree allocates part of its resources to healing wounds and producing shoots or suckers, to the detriment of vertical growth and the formation of its main trunk.

HOW THE CHALLENGE IS ADDRESSED

How to Protect Them?

The choice of the most suitable protection system depends on the animal species present on-site, the type of potential damage, the size of the plants, and the available budget. Mechanical protections, whether individual or collective, create a physical barrier that prevents animals from accessing the trees. These can be partial, targeting specific types of damage, or total, offering comprehensive protection.

Individual protections include solutions such as plastic mesh guards, shelter tubes, metal corsets, and bamboo guards. Collective protections involve enclosing the entire planting area with electric fences, wire mesh, barbed wire, or wooden barriers.

Keywords: Protection, Agroforestry, Trees, Planting, Grazing, Wildlife, Livestock, Fences, Sleeves, Ecosystem

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ADVANTAGES

Advantages of Proper Protection

Adequate tree protection from the moment of planting offers numerous benefits. It ensures the survival of the plants by shielding them from animal damage. It accelerates growth in height and diameter by reducing stress and developmental delays. It also helps lower maintenance and replanting costs while preventing significant financial losses. Additionally, it contributes to producing high-quality timber by minimizing deformations and promoting the formation of a straight trunk.

Additional Information:

Examining damage to the existing surrounding vegetation can help identify the wildlife responsible and determine the most suitable protective measures. Conducting a thorough observation and analysis of the agroforestry environment is therefore essential before starting the planting phase.

The height of the protection must exceed the maximum height of potential injuries caused by wildlife. The diameter of the protection should be chosen based on the type of plant to be safeguarded and its future growth. For plastic mesh sleeves, the material's weight per square meter is an important factor in assessing the protection's resistance and durability.

Proper installation of the protection is critical to its effectiveness. Plastic mesh sleeves must be securely attached to a stake to prevent them from being lifted or torn away by wildlife. Various types of stakes are available, each with specific advantages and disadvantages (e.g., metal, wood, bamboo). For instance, adjustable T-posts allow grazing animals to reach almost up to the base of the tree, facilitating maintenance without requiring mechanical intervention.

Biodegradable protections provide an eco-friendly alternative to plastic sleeves. Versions made from corn or potato starch and biobased carbon materials have been introduced to the European market, but their lifespan remains short (approximately 18 months).

Rodents, such as voles, can cause significant damage to tree roots, particularly in fruit trees. Anti-vole cages and mesh baskets can be installed during planting to protect the roots. Preventive measures, such as soil cultivation and maintaining low herbaceous cover, can also help reduce rodent populations.

The cost of different protection methods can vary significantly. It is important to choose a method that strikes a good balance between cost and effectiveness. For example, electric fences can be expensive to install but provide long-term effective protection over a large area.

Finally, it is crucial to remove tree protections when they are no longer needed—either when the tree is large enough to no longer be vulnerable to wildlife, or if the protection is damaged or starts to embed in the bark. Protections should be carefully removed using proper tools to prevent any damage to the tree. Used protections should be responsibly disposed of through recycling or specialized services.

HIGHLIGHTS:

- **Fences, sleeves, or tailored protections allow for the coexistence of grazing and the safeguarding of agroforestry plantations.**
- **The choice of a protection system depends on site characteristics, animal species, types of damage, plant size, area to protect, budget, material durability, and environmental impact.**
- **Regular monitoring and proper installation of protective measures enhance their long-term effectiveness and help avoid costs associated with losses and replanting.**

Forage hedge with intermittent fencing to protect trees from ewes, and wooden barriers at different levels to allow access during grazing - Ferme de Conflant ©Ver de Terre Production

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